

The Effectiveness of Instagram as a Marketing Tool for Naelofar Hijab

Nornatasya Farina Jasman*

*College of Creative Arts, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor
Email: nornatasyafarinajasman@gmail.com*

Mohamed Razeef Abdul Razak*

*College of Creative Arts, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor
Corresponding author
Email: razeef080@uitm.edu.my*

Azahar Harun*

*College of Creative Arts, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Cawangan Melaka
Email: azahar581@uitm.edu.my*

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** These authors contributed equally to this study*

ABSTRACT

According to a survey conducted by the Malaysia eCommerce Industry, the hijab industry in Malaysia is a very profitable business that is expected to generate US \$5.9 billion by 2024, according to the survey. Because of this, the study investigates the effective marketing strategy of the Naelofar Hijab brand as depicted on the Instagram platform to engage with the target audience. As a successful brand, this is even more important than other aspects of the Instagram marketing strategy. The AIDA model was used to analyze the ten most successful Naelofar Hijab Brand campaigns promoted on the Instagram social media platform. Naelofar Hijab was the most successful Brand that used Instagram as a marketing strategy tool to promote their products and grow their customer base and brand awareness. According to preliminary findings, Naelofar Hijab's marketing communication research is primarily defined as a strategy on Instagram focused on viral marketing techniques to draw the audience's attention to the Brand itself rather than the product itself. Other competitors in the fashion hijab category are also taking advantage of the Instagram platform to market their products. Despite this, the marketing techniques employed by the Naelofar Hijab brand are more distinctive in fostering loyalty, trust, inspiration, and motivation in the Brand, as demonstrated by the Brand's founder, Noor Neelofa on her Instagram account. As a result of the AIDA model approach, the findings of this study will benefit the community by increasing knowledge and strengthening entrepreneurial skills in them, allowing them to develop a successful marketing strategy.

Keywords: *AIDA Model, Instagram, Marketing Tools, Naelofar Hijab*

INTRODUCTION

Naelofar Hijab is a well-known hijab brand in Malaysia, where it competes with several other well-known brands. As Malaysia's Muslim population increases to 61.3 percent of the population, preliminary statistics indicate that demand for the fashionable hijab business is increasing (Amanda, 2020). Following the 2018 report (Atiqah, Hijab Brands in Malaysia, 2019), it has been estimated that the accumulated profit is at least RM 1 billion, which is approximately USD 245 million. With the rise in demand and desire among Muslim women who wear hijab, the fashion industry is seeing an increase in business due to this. Naelofar Hijab, one of the most successful marketing brands in a marketing campaign that builds audience interaction and brand engagement, employs Instagram as one of its marketing strategy tactics to direct audience traffic towards brands and products using a social media approach. Additionally, communication between Naelofar Hijab marketers is being investigated, as this is associated with the spread of viral marketing through the Instagram platform. According to (Beckmann & Bell, May 2001), this is the related research discussed in how Naelofar Hijab communication marketing succeeds through the Instagram platform (Mersid & Merve, 2018), Naelofar Hijab also used a viral marketing platform as a strategy tool to deliver quick information to their target audience, according to the findings of the initial research for this study. The rumors that spread about the founder of the Naelofar Brand, Noor Neelofa, have impacted the Brand. Naelofar Hijab, which recently launched its newest product at the Zouk Club in Kuala Lumpur, was the subject of the previous investigation. It harmed the Brand because it did not correspond to the situation, but the fallout from the rumor had a positive impact on the Brand (Bazlin, Teh, & Gan, 2019).

The Naelofar Hijab brand does not rely solely on traditional mainstream mass media for its consumer advertising; instead, it uses direct channel marketing to reach consumers. This marketing strategy shifts the focus to a new platform, Instagram, to generate online marketing tools for businesses. By developing a marketing strategy for a brand that can provide incredible value. It will be able to significantly increase its ability to expand promotional activities on the Instagram platform, thereby increasing audience interest in the Naelofar Hijab brand and increasing sales (Rafiq & Fulford, 2005) (Victoria & Helen, 2013). It has been suggested by (Goldsmith & Clark, 2008) (Luis, Carlos, & Sergio, Be creative, my friend! Engaging users on Instagram by promoting positive emotion, 2020) the Instagram platform can target businesses more broadly exposed to new target audiences and build brand engagement by promoting positive emotion. In addition, competitors in the hijab fashion industry have chosen the Instagram platform to promote their respective brands. (Socialbakers, 2019) (Luis, Carlos, & Sergio, Be creative, my friend! Engaging users on Instagram by promoting positive emotion, 2020), The promotion of positive emotion on Instagram has proven effective in increasing engagement and revenue for fashion brands in 2020. public (Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2017b). That is because advertising campaigns that engage target audiences and attract new followers to Instagram accounts rely on creativity and originality to be successful. Instagram is a powerful tool in the fashion industry, helping to increase brand publishing and campaign promotion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

New media is likely to focus on the hijab fashion industry's marketing strategy. That new media type has more to do with the media, such as social media platforms, than ever before. The Hijab fashion industry relies heavily on social media to connect with its consumers and followers in Malaysia. That is because social media is a strategic and practical platform for promoting a society in an easy, low-cost, free advertising, fast-medium, and widely spreading manner. The Hijab fashion industry relied heavily on Instagram to distribute free advertising online. When it comes to attracting new consumers, social media

has features that can help a business become more advanced in its marketing efforts. IGTV, IG Live, Share Stories, Repost, Shop, Video, and Visual are just some ways that Instagram gives users the freedom to experiment with the various tools at their disposal (Fournier, 1998; Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001; Ana & Natascha, 2016).

Instagram as a Marketing Communication

Since Instagram users and followers are more likely to engage with a brand or product when using the app, it is at the center of the marketing communication strategy used to promote it. Online marketing relies on Instagram as the primary social media platform for interacting with consumers. Instagram was built with interactivity features in mind to get more out of their time on the service. By achieving their goals, users utilize Instagram's platform as a digital marketing tool. There are many reasons why Instagram is the ideal platform for businesses to collaborate with their marketing communications to ensure that their interactions with their consumers are effective. (Dahan & Hauser, 2002; Ana & Natascha, 2016), this platform makes it simple and easy for brands to engage with their consumers more meaningfully. This is because online marketing can facilitate the promotion of a brand through the visual posting of the product, which attracts potential consumers' attention. In December 2016, Instagram had more than 600 million active users, most of whom used the app to access the service (Statista, 2017; Washington, 2014; Nathaniel, Jay, & Hyoyeun, 2017). This is the most dynamic platform for an influencer to promote their product or brand among other users.

I. Price Strategy in Visual

When marketing a product's value to consumers, price is critical for a successful strategy. Placement of price is one of the strategies used because it influences the consumers' decision to purchase goods or products. Product prices can be visually quoted on Instagram by describing unique product characteristics in an ad design. The price points for the items have been set following industry standards while also considering the item's unique characteristics, such as its material or design. The product itself, which has characteristics that distinguish it from other business products, can significantly impact sales because of the low prices it offers to buyers. Higher prices are also associated with products with a premium value in terms of quality and uniqueness and high-quality products. When determining the value of a product, the price should be given particular consideration because it affects the profit and adds value to the item being evaluated. Therefore, prices should be displayed visually to convey information without causing consumers to doubt or wonder about what they are purchasing (Išoraitė, 2016; Muhammad, 2019). Additionally, it can provide customers with a sense of fulfillment when they purchase products at a reasonable price (Muhammad, 2019).

II. Promotion Strategy in Visual

Promoting a product or service is the next step in the marketing mix, and it includes a variety of elements such as public relations, advertising, social media marketing, video advertising on various platforms, and more (Muhammad, 2019). Medium strategy is used to attract consumers to a business's marketing of a product or service offered for sale. It is one of the methods that can attract the attention of many consumers by offering various promotions on products such as discounts, purchasing items that are purchased on a free one-time basis, or giving away free items. Every promotion must go through an exciting process for the product or service's marketing strategy to run smoothly and attract more

consumers to the market compared to competing businesses. As a part of the process of brand promotion, it can also assist a company in introducing new products or services to the market (Muchiri, 2016; Muhammad, 2019).

The visuals displayed have the potential to capture the attention of Instagram users, primarily since the promotion is carried out by using numbers as a factor in attracting users' attention. An advertising strategy that involves placing the amount, number, and value of a product in a business stake to attract customers and a new target audience is called direct marketing. According to (Muhammad, 2019), a marketing strategy can be broken down into several categories. These categories include mass media advertising, sales promotion (coupons, lotteries, and discount vouchers), public relations (media introduction or PR event), personal selling, direct marketing, and digital marketing, which includes social media platforms. Businesses require information about their consumers or target markets, which is done to gather information about their requirements and preferences.

III. Platform Strategy to Market

Naelofar Hijab Brand began in September 2014. Observations show that Instagram Naelofar Hijab Brand conducts marketing strategies via an internet connection. It promoted the product and the brand on various social media platforms, which resulted in a significant increase in sales. Consumers prefer to spend their time on social media platforms like Instagram. In the marketing of trendy brands, social media is an important platform, according to (Nurfatin, Shantiny, & Komathy, 2018). Trendy products and brands are the most sought-after by social media users. This is the case because of the ease, speed, and wide reach that social media platforms provide for product and brand promotion.

In addition, new features such as Reels and an IG shop have been added to the Instagram platform, making it easier for users to make purchases directly from the social media platform. According to (Dahan & Hauser, 2002; Ana & Natascha, 2016), the Instagram platform is a practical and usable medium for collaborating with marketing communication to make its interaction onward the business and the consumer more effectively efficient. Improving brand interaction with customers is effortless and seamless when using this platform.

Influencers as Brand Icons

Individuals who can persuade potential consumers of the merits of a particular product or service by promoting or endorsing the brand product on social media platforms are known as influencers in marketing communication. Influencers play a crucial role in marketing by establishing credibility by encouraging social media users or consumers to promote branded products. Influencer marketing, particularly on social media platforms such as Instagram, is one of the communication marketing strategies that involve the support of celebrities as an endorsement of a brand's product (Freberg, Graham, McGauhey, & Freberg, 2010; Aziz, et al., 2019; Tahirah, et al., 2020). Partnerships with social media influencers or celebrities with a large following are being used by businesses to reach over 100 million followers to endorse their brand (Hanson, 2018; Hashim, et al., 2020; Tahirah, et al., 2020). A brand's marketing can benefit from the engagement and follower traffic that influencers generate because their followers are more likely to engage with its product.

For marketing strategy tools to be successful, influencers or brand ambassadors play a crucial role. As the brand's founder, Noor Neelofa uses her name to sway other people, especially fans of the brand. Various multinational corporations attempt to control her brand as she is a celebrity and an ambassador for them. Consequently, she takes the brand with her wherever she goes to expand the market for business. Artist Noor Neelofa is constantly creating new hijab designs that can satisfy any woman's desires and a variety of distinctive but appealing and straightforward styles. Her work is recognized worldwide as women's fashion (Nurfatin, Shantiny, & Komathy, 2018). Naelofar Hijab's publicity strategy is to draw an audience by using Noor Neelofa as an influential style icon because the look she sports can inspire and motivate other women. Noor Neelofa uses the brand to extend her persona while also promoting it in every TV commercial she has appeared in.

(Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017), argue that this will increase the legitimacy of the brand's connection with Instagram users, who regard Instagram as a source of information (Daniel, Marta, & Sergio, 2019). It guided the audience to a higher level of trustworthiness based on this performance. Because of her influence in generating interest, the influencer can direct traffic from followers to the brand. Influences are critical when influencing an audience because they serve as icons or idols, projecting a positive image, aura, and motivation to the audience. The vast majority of influencers are celebrities and well-known individuals who can promote a business, brand, or product to a target audience through their social media platforms. This is because they have a loyal following and supporters. As a result, influencers used their Instagram accounts to publish or evaluate the product and brand to their followers, increasing the audience. The traffic audience and the new target audience will grow significantly due to the engagement generated by the influencers' postings or reviews due to the implementation of this strategy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Through the use of the Instagram platform, this aims to demonstrate a technique for monitoring the phenomenological study on the interaction of marketing communication on the Naelofar Hijab Brand. This processing method is likely to result in a better understanding of Hijab brand marketing communication research through Instagram, as well as the development of a new process for developing a model from marketing strategy data that will assist companies in the long run in moving in a more strategic and practical direction, according to the authors. The research plan is an essential component of this chapter, and it includes the current literature on the topic of relevant study, technique, procedure, the process of models, analytical method, and ethical considerations, among other things.

Observation on the Naelofar Hijab marketing strategy tool assessed campaigns on the Instagram platform using the modern-day AIDA model. The AIDA methodology was used to analyze ten successful Naelofar Hijab campaigns that utilized Instagram, a social media platform included in the brand's marketing strategy. The purpose of this study is to ascertain the most effective Naelofar Hijab campaign procedure in marketing and to foster relationships and loyalty between the audience and brands. Interviews were used to conduct empirical research to elicit reliable and valid data for data analysis using the AIDA model. The researcher established objectives for determining, exploring, identifying, and developing level strategies to ensure the success of marketing campaigns based on the data.

Figure 1. AIDA model

FINDINGS

Figure 2. Findings

Figure 3. Creative Visual Posting on Naelofar Hijab Brand Instagram

(Source: https://www.instagram.com/p/B_d-IDIJwPO/)

Figure 4. Creative Advertising Post by Naelofar Hijab Brand
(Source: https://www.instagram.com/p/B_d-IDIJwPO/)

Brand advertisements on Instagram Naelofar Hijab are evaluated using the AIDA model. This strategy is applied to the Naelofar Hijab Brand to examine ten successful campaigns utilizing an Instagram marketing tool to drive audience traffic to the brand effectively. The AIDA Model, which is hierarchical, explains how Instagram followers are directed toward making purchases related to the Brand's interest. The AIDA model, which is order-based, depicts how Instagram followers make purchases from a business. As a result, the process increases followers' contact with the Brand and elicits emotions, resulting in a more fulfilling and enjoyable brand experience. The experience may result in creating a new target audience based on feedback.

I. Awareness

Figure 4 shows the Naelofar Hijab Instagram visual posting. This is shown in the graphics used to inform consumers about the Brand release. The visible Instagram posting expresses concepts and inspiration for the audience and hijab-style women. Each new Naelofar Hijab product will have a new graphic release to appeal to consumers, and this campaign will also raise awareness among hijabista.

II. Interest

The theory reaction is a user's or customer's emotional reaction to anything they see. The show's visual content will interact with mirrored sentiments and emotions, and it does so by communicating with users or customers to communicate their intentions through feelings and sensations. Involving users or clients in the Instagram post will elicit emotions and feelings. The goal of users or consumers is reflected in their likes, feedback, or comments (Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2017a; Luis, Carlos, & Sergio, Be creative, my friend! Engaging users on Instagram by promoting positive emotions, 2021).

III. Desires

This can lead to building desire while meeting commitments. Marketing communication relies on a commitment to understanding needs and wishes. Commitment is a necessary function in long-term relationships.

IV. Action

This visual marketing campaign will encourage campaign recipients to take action and learn more about the Brand. This occurs when a consumer wants to learn more about a brand before purchasing it or leaving the items related to placing an ad.

CONCLUSION

To summarize the findings of this study, the researchers discovered a wealth of new knowledge and information about the marketing communication strategy instruments that are currently in use in the business world. By increasing knowledge and strengthening entrepreneurial abilities, the findings of this case study can be used as a practical guide for businesses and the community in developing marketing strategies by increasing knowledge and strengthening entrepreneurial abilities. This study demonstrates how businesses can better understand marketing strategy tools to generate effective campaigns by attracting traffic to the Instagram platform through a game-like strategy. The following procedure may result in developing a marketing strategy process that can assist the company to move in a more strategic and practical direction. In addition, the AIDA Model approach is employed in this case.

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